

Supplementary Material to "Betweenness Centrality in Spatial Networks: A Spatially Normalised Approach"

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Abstract

Centrality metrics are essential to network analysis. They reveal important morphological properties of networks, indicating e.g. node or edge importance. Applications are manifold, ranging from biology to transport planning. However, while being commonly applied in spatial contexts such as urban analytics, the implications of the spatial configuration of network elements on these metrics are widely neglected. As a consequence, a systematic bias is introduced into spatial network analyses. When applied to real-world problems, unintended side effects and wrong conclusions might be the result. In this paper, we assess the impact of node density on betweenness centrality. Furthermore, we propose a method for computing spatially normalised betweenness centrality. We apply it to a theoretical case as well as real-world transport networks. Results show that spatial normalisation mitigates the prevalent bias of node density.

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Supplementary Material *Other (Code and examples)*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125632>

1 Introduction

In this supplementary document we provide additional examples for spatially weighted betweenness centrality c_{SB} applied to real-world urban road networks. We further compare the results to standard edge betweenness centrality c_B and highlight the differences. For interactive assessment of the results and computation of individual examples we provide the source code including a Jupyter notebook as well as network data online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125632>. Furthermore, you find the original GIScience short paper at <https://doi.org/10.4230/LIPIcs.GIScience.2023.83>.

2 Results for real-world urban road networks

2.1 Denver

Figure 1 Betweenness centrality for a subset of Denver, Colorado (USA)

For the given subset of the street network of Denver we can observe a very regular grid pattern of roads which is broken up by a park in the South and some block subdivisions as shown in figure 1 d). Node density within the given extract from OpenStreetMap is highest in the West and along the roads surrounding the park in the South. Standard edge betweenness centrality c_B emphasises edges linking origins and destinations in the West and in direction NW-SE (subfigure a). In contrast, spatially normalised centrality c_{SB} highlights segments on the NE-SW relation as visible in subfigure b).

2.2 Karlsruhe

■ **Figure 2** Betweenness centrality for a subset of Karlsruhe, Germany

A prominent feature of the Karlsruhe street network is the circular ring around the Karlsruhe Palace, with streets radiating from the palace, forming a fan-like structure. Node densities slightly vary, with significantly lower density in the North and few clusters in the South and East. Accordingly, edge betweenness centrality c_B is highest on shortest paths linking these clusters, mainly South of the centre. c_{SB} mitigates this effect and leads to high centrality being focused on edges in proximity to the spatial centre of the chosen area. Furthermore, c_{SB} creates a more homogeneous distribution of centrality when comparing the network in the North and South.

2.3 Leeds

■ **Figure 3** Betweenness centrality for a subset of Leeds, UK

The network extract for Leeds shows an inhomogeneous pattern with high node density in the North-East and at some locations in the West and South. c_B accordingly is highest for paths linking these areas, especially in the corridor NE-SW. In contrast, c_{SB} is more homogeneous with high centrality prevalent at the spatial centre. It also attributes higher centrality to edges linking the area in the North-West which are of relatively low centrality using c_B .

2.4 Mannheim

■ **Figure 4** Betweenness centrality for a subset of Mannheim, Germany

The Mannheim case is characterised by a regular grid structure with some of the blocks offering shortcuts such as in a park located south of the centre. Despite the regular structure, node densities vary e.g. due to availability of additional footpaths or presence of parking facilities at the market square (north of centre). Standard betweenness centrality c_B pronounces relations from and to these areas with high node density. For example, the parking lot at the market square north of the centre generates high centrality values on its access roads as visible in 4 a). This effect is compensated with spatially normalised betweenness centrality c_{SB} as in figure 4 b). Both approaches to centrality highlight the relevance of diagonal paths present in the park for shortest paths. c_B is relatively low for edges that connect the area in the North-East, which is compensated in c_{SB} .

2.5 New York

■ **Figure 5** Betweenness centrality for a subset of New York, USA

The subset of New York shows a regular grid pattern with one central road crossing the blocks in a different angle and a park that breaks up the block structure. Nodes are clustered at several intersections and at the park. The spatial pattern of centrality values is very similar when comparing c_B with c_{SB} . However, edges in SW to North direction in the West are attributed higher centrality with c_{SB} , forming another high-centrality corridor besides the main corridors in the centre.

2.6 Paris

■ **Figure 6** Betweenness centrality for a subset of Paris, France

For Paris, the subset of the road network shows an irregular pattern and is further characterised by the river that branches out and forms natural barriers. Several bridges maintain network connectivity and are expected to show high values of centrality. Furthermore, towards the North, node density is higher than average as well as at a smaller area in the South-East. Both, c_B as well as c_{SB} show the expected high centrality at bridges. However, c_B pronounces relations on the N-SE corridor and relatively low centrality values towards the South-West. c_{SB} is distributed more homogeneously.

2.7 Zurich

■ **Figure 7** Betweenness centrality for a subset of Zurich, Switzerland

The extract for Zurich represents a subset of the old town which is characterised by parts with high connectivity and accordingly high node density as well as less connected periphery and a natural barrier in form of a river in the centre. Comparing c_{SB} with c_B we can observe many similarities - e.g. high centrality for the bridges crossing the river. However, c_B emphasises segments on the relation SW-NE and in the North, where areas with high node density are connected. c_{SB} shows slightly lower centrality on these relations, while slightly emphasising edges on the West-East corridor as well as towards the South-East.

3 Closing Remarks

We randomly selected the examples presented in this document from urban street networks of different form. The purpose of these examples is to highlight the differences between standard edge betweenness centrality c_B and our proposed spatially normalised betweenness centrality c_{SB} . However, due to arbitrary choice of subsets the results for centrality might not adequately represent the importance of segments for everyday mobility in the given cities. For such assessment, appropriate areas of interest need to be defined and edge effects have to be regarded.